

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COOPERATIVE AND NON-COOPERATIVE SMALL-SCALE POULTRY FARMERS' USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

*¹Idowu O. B., ¹Ajah J., ¹Fadiji T. O. and ³Paul A.H.

¹Department of Extension and Rural Sociology, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

³Department of Economics and Extension Federal University, Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

*¹Corresponding Author: eboreimebolanle@gmail.com. +2348035980949

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ABSTRACT:

The study analysed the cooperative and non-cooperative small-scale poultry farmers' use of information and communication technologies in North Central Nigeria. The sample comprised 360 cooperative small-scale poultry farmers and 360 non-cooperative small-scale poultry farmers. Data for the study were collected through a well-structured questionnaire. The data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Generally, the result of the study indicated that there was a significant difference in the cooperative and non-cooperative small scale poultry farmers' use of all ICTs; the result also indicated that there was a significant interaction effect between cooperative membership and location, the result as well showed that there were locational differences in the use of ICTs by cooperative and non-cooperative small scale poultry farmers. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that efforts be made to sensitise farmers on the benefits of belonging to a cooperative society, as this will benefit and aid their access to inputs and training for increased production.

Keywords: Poultry, information and communication technologies, cooperatives

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector and cooperative society play an important role in developing a country's economy. Integrating the agriculture sector with cooperatives activities pave the way towards transformation and development through improved access to agricultural inputs and markets, income enhancement and access to social services (Kumburu and Pande, 2020). A cooperative society is a voluntary association of individuals who come together to meet their social, economic and cultural needs. Cooperatives are formed and operated based on cooperation

principles and values. Karakas (2019) defines cooperative societies as "autonomous groups of people who voluntarily join together with common purposes and objectives to meet socio-economic needs and goals through democratically managed and owned associations".

Membership in farmers' cooperative society is important because it aims to empower individuals by enabling them to collectively address their needs and aspirations in a fair and equitable manner. Smallholder farmers tend to benefit from

cooperatives in that those interventions or facilities they cannot get access to, cooperative membership opens an avenue for them to access them.

Poultry production is an industrious firm in the agricultural sector, as there are many opportunities involved, ranging from feed formulation to management at poultry farms. Most of the world's sources of protein are derived from animals, with poultry products at the forefront, from eggs to meat (Adeyemo and Onikoyi, 2012). The impact of the poultry industry on Nigeria's economy should not be overlooked. However, most of the poultry farmers in rural areas are small-scale farmers with little or no exposure to the current global trends in ICT. Though a few are acquainted with ICT, they do not have the means to acquire advanced technologies or even relevant information on how to use them. However, membership in a cooperative society provides an avenue for these poultry farmers to get in touch with relevant sectors and stakeholders that will enhance their knowledge and benefit them on the issues surrounding the use of ICT and also the activities involved in the poultry industry to better their lives and move their business further.

In North Central Nigeria, the poultry farming sector is crucial in contributing to the region's economic development and food security. However, a significant gap exists in our understanding of the dynamics and effectiveness of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) adoption within this sector, particularly when comparing cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farming systems. The problem at hand stems from the lack of comprehensive research that specifically investigates and compares how cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers utilise ICTs (Olaniyi, 2013). Current literature tends to overlook the distinct challenges and opportunities faced

by these two groups, thereby hindering the development of targeted strategies and policies to enhance ICT integration for improved productivity, sustainability, and overall development of the poultry farming industry in North Central Nigeria.

This study seeks to address this gap by conducting a comparative analysis of cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers' use of ICTs in the region. By identifying the disparities in technology adoption, understanding the factors influencing these differences, and assessing the impact on farm efficiency and outcomes, the research aims to provide valuable insights that can inform policies and interventions tailored to the specific needs of each farming structure. Ultimately, addressing this problem will contribute to the advancement of the poultry farming sector and foster sustainable agricultural practices in North Central Nigeria. Studies by Benjamin *et al.* (2018), Folitse, Manteaw, Dzandu, Obeng-Koranteng and Bekoe (2019); Shemei, Zhanli, Wanglin and Vladislav (2019); Zhang, Sun, Ma and Valentinov (2020); and Olanrewaju, Akintunde, Busari and Omotosho (2023) employed descriptive statistics for their studies' objectives, while none utilised a three-way ANOVA.

The objectives of the study were to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers in the study area, compare the ICT used by cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers and analyse the level of ICT usage by cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. This is one of the six geo-political zones in the country and is made up of 7 states which include: Kwara State, Kogi State, Niger

State, Nasarawa State, Benue State, Plateau State and the Federal Capital Territory. The study area is located between latitude 10° 20' 00" N and longitude 7° 45' 00" E. The largest state in the zone is Niger State, with a land mass of 76,363 square kilometres, while the smallest state in the zone, with a land mass of 27 117 square kilometres, is Benue State.

The zone is characterized by two distinct seasons: the rainy season, which lasts from May to October, and the dry season, which lasts from December to March. The zone experiences a variety of volumes and durations of precipitation. There are transitional months between these two seasons in April and November. While the dry season typically peaks in February and March with very high temperatures, the rainy season typically peaks in August. The harmattan period, typically defined as November through January, is characterized by chilly, dry weather brought on by the northeast trade wind (Ahmed and Mohammed, 2015).

The research area's vegetation is often grass-dominated and a hybrid of the natural biomes of the southern and northern Guinea Savanna. Because of the favourable meteorological and ecological conditions in north-central Nigeria, the region has gained the title of "food basket of the nation."

2.2 Data Collection

Data for the study were collected both from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires that were validated by experts in the Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology at the University of Abuja. After the validation, the questionnaires were administered to respondents with the assistance of ADP-trained enumerators. Data were collected on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, and ICT tools used by poultry farmers' usage of ICT tools (GSM Phones, Radio, Television, Computer, Email, WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Zoom and Agricultural books). Data were also collected on the constraints that affect poultry farmers' usage of ICT tools in North Central Nigeria.

2.3 Methods of Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in data analysis. Objectives 1 was achieved using descriptive statistics such as percentage and frequency tables, while objectives 2 and 3 were achieved using an analysis of variance. (ANOVA), and using a 5-point Likert scale rating. The hypotheses were tested at a 0.05% level of significance using the Bonferroni model. The three-way mixed analysis of variance (ANOVA) is mathematically expressed as:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \beta_6 \ln X_6 \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where:

- i denotes the level of factor C (Cooperative membership)
- j denotes the level of factor L (Location, i.e., States)
- k denotes the level of factor I (ICTs-type)
- t denotes the ith observation in cell or

treatment (ijt)

Y_{ijkt} = Individual cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmer's response indicating his/her usage of ICTs.

μ = population mean

C_i = Refers to the effect of cooperative

membership (Co-Member) on the use of ICTs (main effect of cooperative membership).

L_i = Refers to differences in the use of ICTs due to location (Nasarawa, Plateau, Kwara, Kogi, Abuja, Benue). This measures the main effect of location (state).

I_k = Refers to the effect of ICTs-type (main effect of ICTs-type).

CL_{ij} = interaction effect of Cooperative membership and location (Co-MemberLocation).

GI_{ik} = interaction effect of cooperative membership and ICTs-type (Co-Member*ICTs-type).

LI_{ik} = interaction effect of location and ICTs-type (Location*ICTs-type)

GLI_{ijk} = interaction effect of cooperative membership, location and ICTs-type (Co-MemberlocationICTs-type).

e_{ijkl} = error term.

Here, the three factors considered to influence poultry farmers' use of ICTs are the cooperative membership, location (state), and the nature of ICTs, denoted as ICTs-Type. Cooperative membership has two levels (cooperative member and non-cooperative member) while the location has six levels (Nasarawa, Plateau, Kwara, Kogi, Abuja, Benue states) and ICTs-type has ten levels (GSM phones Radio, Television (TV), Computer, Email, WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Zoom, Agricultural Books). The factor, ICTs-type, is a repeated measure variable (within factors), while cooperative membership (Co-Membership) and location were between factor variables. By interpretation, the model states that poultry farmers' use of ICTs (Y_{ijkl}) depends on

cooperative membership (C_i), location of the poultry farmer, that is, the state where the poultry farmer is working (L_i), ICTs-type (I_k), the interaction of cooperative membership and location (CL_{ij}), the interaction of cooperative membership and ICTs-type (CI_{ik}), the interaction of location and ICTs-type (LI_{ik}) and the joint effect of cooperative membership, location and ICTs-type (GLI_{ijk}). The population mean (μ) does not contribute to any variation in the observed differences, while e_{ijkl} is the error term. SPSS 18.0 was used to run the analysis and tested at a 5 per cent probability level. Mean separation was done using the Bonferroni model.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Cooperative and Non-cooperative Poultry Farmers in North Central Nigeria

Information on the socioeconomic characteristics of the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers is shown in Table 1. The gender distribution of the cooperative poultry farmers sampled indicated that only 33.7% were female, while 67.3% were male. Meanwhile, for non-cooperative poultry farmers, only 30.9% were female and 69.1% were male. This indicates a prevalence of male poultry farmers in the study area. This observation aligns with findings from Kalio (2020), who similarly noted that most poultry farmers in Yenagoa Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, were predominantly male.

In terms of age, most cooperative poultry farmers were adults between the ages of 45 and 55 years, while the non-cooperative poultry farmers were adults between the ages of 45 and 55 years. The mean age suggested that most poultry farmers, irrespective of cooperative membership, were still at a productive age and could

carry out production effectively. The findings also indicated that both cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers possessed educational backgrounds, with percentages of 86.3% and 86.1%, respectively. The educational level plays a good role in the utilization of new and innovative production methods and undertaking risks. This coincides with the findings of Benjamin et al. (2018), who asserted that educated poultry farmers in Ghana were more inclined towards adopting Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

The years of farming experience were analysed, and it revealed that about (80%) of respondents (both cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers) have been farming for about 1-15 years have been farming, (and 10%) of the farmers' have spent approximately 16 years. Indeed, experience goes along with skill acquisition, which is fundamental to efficiency and effectiveness in any job operation. The result implies that most of the farmers, irrespective of membership, have acquired reasonable years of experience in farming, which has spread effects on agricultural development.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents North Central Nigeria (irrespective of location)

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents	Cooperative (360)		Non-Cooperative (360)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Age of Respondents				
= 25	6	1.7	10	2.8
26-35	97	26.7	125	34.5
36-45	103	28.7	59	16.4
46-55	119	33.7	136	37.9
>55	35	9.7	30	8.4
Gender				
Male	238	66.3	248	69.1
Female	122	33.7	112	30.9
Educational Status				
No Education	19	5.3	22	6.1
Primary	19	5.3	24	6.7
Secondary	77	21.2	86	23.7
NCE	96	26.7	99	27.6
OND/HSC	138	38.4	125	34.8
B.Sc/HND	11	3.1	4	1.1
Farming Experience				
1-10	213	59.1	192	53.2
11-15	108	30.1	129	35.9
>16	37	10.9	39	10.9

Source: Field data analysis, 2023

3.2 Analysis of the Use of ICTs among Cooperative and Non-cooperative Members

Table 2 shows the result of the 3-way mixed ANOVA to assess the use of ICTs by cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers. This model provided the avenue to look at data from two perspectives, i.e.,

assessing the main effects of the factors and their interaction effects. It should be noted that each row in Table 2 provided answers to the study's objectives. Therefore, each factor and their interactions were interpreted separately to enhance the comprehension of the results.

Sources of variation	Df	SS	MS	F-cal	P-value
ICTs-type	9	9565.38	1062.82	521.53	.00
Location*ICTs-type	45	1327.26	29.495	14.47	.00
Co-member*ICTs-type	9	304.38	33.82	16.59	.00
Co-member*location*ICTs-type	45	383.18	8.52	4.18	.00
Error (within subjects)	6372	12985.40	2.04		
Location	5	45.32	9.07	12.25	.00
Co-membership	1	9.43	9.43	12.74	.00
Co-member location	5	19.94	3.99	5.39	.00
Error (between subjects)	708	523.96	0.74		

Table 2: ANOVA results of the Cooperative and Non-Cooperative Farmers' use of ICTs

Source: Field data analysis, 2023

3.3 Cooperative and Non-cooperative Poultry Farmers' Use of ICTs (pooled data)

The results of using all ICTs by the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers are shown in Figure 1. It showed how the membership of a cooperative society affects the use of ICTs. The question to be answered is: regardless of location and types of ICTs, did the utilization of ICT depend on membership in a cooperative society? It tested the null hypothesis, which states that H_0 : there is no significant difference in the use of ICTs among the cooperative and non-

cooperative poultry farmers' use of ICTs in the study area (μ cooperative use of all ICTs = μ non-cooperative use of all ICTs). The result, $F(708) = 12.74$, $P = .00$, indicates that the use of ICTs among cooperative and non-cooperative farmers significantly ($p < .05$) differed, hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The mean separation (Figure 1) shows that the use of ICTs among the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers significantly differed ($p < .05$) from each other. This means that both the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers do

not use all the ICTs at an equal rate. This is in line with the findings of Khadijat *et al.* (2023), who opined that membership in cooperative society influenced the massive utilization of ICT. This is probably so because membership in a cooperative society gives member farmers a higher advantage in being able to source information and get knowledge about

particular trends faster and easier than non-members. New ideas spread faster in a close-knit society as cooperative members are able to share information among themselves because they tend to see each other frequently and may likely have group platforms used in disseminating information to their members.

Figure 1: Effect of cooperative membership on the use of all ICTs in NCN (pooled data)

Note: Mean with the same alphabet did not significantly differ

3.4 Cooperative and Non-Cooperative Poultry Farmer's Use of Each ICTs-type Across North Central Zone (pooled data)

Figure 2 provides information on how poultry farmers' membership affects ICT usage (pooled data from all states). The question is: regardless of location (states), did the use of each ICT depend on membership? The result, $F(9, 6372) = 51.53$, $p = .00$, shows that there is a significant ($p < .05$) difference in the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers' use of ICT. This shows that membership of the cooperative society

significantly ($p < .05$) affects the usage of a particular ICT.

Mean separation was carried out to identify the effect of cooperative membership on using each ICT. The outcome (Figure 2) showed that the use of mobile phones by the non-cooperative members and cooperative poultry farmers is the same. That is, the use of mobile phones is similar between the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers. The usage of WhatsApp, Facebook, agribook, email, and TV platforms among the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers

significantly ($p < .05$) differed. This shows that cooperative poultry farmers used these ICTs more than non-cooperative poultry farmers. The result in Figure 2 further showed that both the cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers used the radio and computer equally. This aligns with the

finding of Olaniyi (2013), who stated that ICT is the 'wheel' of economic activities since it facilitates economic growth. This may be why cooperative and non-cooperative poultry farmers use ICT to facilitate economic growth.

Figure 2: Effect of Cooperative membership on the use of each ICT (pooled data)

Note: Mean with the same alphabet did not significantly differ

3.5 Analysis of the Use of all ICTs in North Central Nigeria

The results presented in Figure 3 demonstrate a significantly higher adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) compared to other states in the North Central region. This observation implies that the developed and expansively covered capital, Abuja, likely contributes to a greater familiarity among poultry farmers with the use of ICT. Moreover, the data suggests that poultry farmers in Abuja and Benue exhibit more exposure to ICTs than their counterparts in Kwara, Kogi,

Nasarawa, and Plateau States, where the utilisation of ICT is relatively lower. The educational background of respondents and the presence of a higher number of youths of a productive age may be contributing factors. Younger individuals are known to adopt technology more readily, and educational attainment often influences farm management practices and overall agricultural production. This aligns with the findings of Olanrewaju *et al.* (2023), who highlighted the pivotal role of education in adopting new and innovative production methods and the willingness to undertake risks in farming practices.

Figure 3: Effect of Location (States) on the use of all ICTs in NCN (pooled data)

Note: Mean with the same alphabet did not significantly differ

4.1 CONCLUSION

From this study, it is conclusive that the cooperative poultry farmers in North Central Nigeria use ICT more than the non-cooperative poultry farmers. The cooperative farmers have more access to information on the use of ICTs than the non-cooperative poultry farmers as it is easier for them to source information as a group and access grants and other benefits of cooperative. There is a need to have other farmers join a cooperative society to enable them access information and benefits as well.

Efforts should be made by ADPs in the States to initiate a sensitization workshop so that non-cooperative poultry farmers can be sensitized on the advantages of belonging to a cooperative society in the region. Agricultural extension services in the North Central Zone should train the poultry farmers on using Zoom and Twitter, as they were the least used ICT tools in the study area, to improve their knowledge and enable them to follow global trends and not be left behind.

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